

**1-TOM, 11-SON
ANALYSIS OF POEM
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Abstract: Poetry is one of the richest forms of literature, which in itself includes all elements of language a human learns; by elements, the focus is on the rhetorical devices. The witty use of terms used in the reference to things is represented by the rhetorical devices. The aim of the study is to identify the types of creative references used by the poets in order to distinguish their style of writing and group the work into segments. On the basis of each such prominent feature such as rhymes or alliteration, one can determine the boundary or similarity percentage among the poems, which can then be further extended to compare the poet's writing style. The analysis technique is useful for examining different poets of the modern and renaissance periods, since it can be helpful in contrasting their way of putting things into words.

Key words: Keywords NLP Analysis of Poem, Poem Analysis, Poem Classification, Poem Comparison, Poem Qualifiers, Poet Classification, Poetry Analysis, Poetry Recommendation System

Poems have a lyrical quality that is pleasing to the ear, from flowing words to rhythmic beats. To fully comprehend poetry, you must unpack it; examine each element on its own to see what a poem means. What is poetry analysis? To understand the literary work in its entirety, poetry analysis involves examining the independent parts of a poem. Line by line, reading poems allows you to break them down into their order, form, tone, metrical pattern, and theme. Literary analysis is used to understand the meaning of a poem and appreciate it on a deeper level. When analyzing poetry, 5 things to consider include words, rhythm, and structure. They tell a tale and create a storyline that is unique to poetic verse. When reading poems in depth, pay attention to the following main points: identify the main points.

1. Describe the following points. Theme: poetry often conveys a message in figurative terms. The central idea and the subject matter of a poem can reveal the main story of the poem.

2. Language: language influences the mood and tone of a poem, from word choice to imagery. The way a word is organized also influences the tone of a poem.

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3. Describe the following points: Sound and rhythm: the syllabic patterns and stresses create the metrical structure of a poem.

4. Structure: the structure of a poem determines how it is supposed to be read. A poet sculpts their story around stanzas, line breaks, rhyme patterns, punctuation, and pauses.

5. Context: a poem's who, what, where, when, and why can help it explain its purpose. To understand the meaning of a poem, look at these elements.

How to analyze a poem in ten steps reading poetry is a rewarding experience in and of itself. You'll want to study the qualities and characteristics of each poem to see how all of the elements of a poem mesh together. To analyze a poem, follow this step-by-step guide: using this template, you will learn how to read it.

1. Describe the following points. Read the poem. Read it to yourself the first time you approach a poem. Read it slowly, recognizing the nuances and details that may be lost if you read it quickly. Examine the title of the poem and how it relates to the piece's meaning.

2. Read the poem again, this time aloud. Poetry is intended to be read aloud due to its rhythmic patterns. Watch as you read a poem aloud, pay attention to how the words and syllables influence the tone. It would also be helpful to hear someone else read the poem. If you can, search for a recording of the poem on the internet. Listen to how the words move from line to line, where the breaks are made, and where the tension is placed.

3. Describe the following points: Set up a rhyme scheme. If a poem has a rhyme scheme or is written in free verse (i.e. a poem with a rhyme scheme will catch on immediately). Without a rhyme scheme or regular meter). Determine the rhyming scheme by assigning a letter to each line and allowing lines to rhyme the same letter. See if there is a distinct pattern and a formal rhyme scheme, such as terza rima (three-line stanzas with a resemblance to aba bcb, etc.).

4. Scans the poem. The meter of poetry is determined by the order of stressed and unstressed syllables in each line, according to scansion. Mark each foot—the basic measurement of a poetic line consisting of one stressed syllable joined with at least one unstressed syllable. Next, mark the pattern of stresses along the route. Based on this information, you can determine the meter. A poem in iambic pentameter, for example, will have five feet with the syllabic pattern of da dum, da dum, da dum, da dum, da dum, da dum.

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5. Break down the hierarchy. Take a step back and look at the poem on the page. Notice the white space between the words. Poetry is meant to make a visual as well as an emotional statement. Look at the specifics of this structure, such as how many lines are in each stanza. Take a look at the lines that cross the room. Is the end of every line coincident with the end of the thought? If not, the poet may be using an enjambment, in which one line continues into the next.

6. Determine the theme of the poem. In your poem review, note what kind of poem you're reading based on the facts you've analyzed. A sonnet is a poem that has three quatrains (four-line stanzas) followed by a couplet, for example. Sestina, haiku, and limerick poetry are among the other formal forms of poetry.

7. Study the meaning of the poem. Poets make deliberate sentence choices to create their poems. Examine each word and its place in the line and the poem. How does it contribute to the story? Look up words you don't know. See how the poet manipulates language by means of metaphors, similes, and figurative terms. Observe any literary techniques used to shape the poem's syntax, such as alliteration and assonance.

8. Study the meaning of the poem. As you read the poem's structure, pay attention to the text and message to uncover the theme. To understand the historical context of the poem, learn when it was written. Find out where it was written and what language the poet used. If you're reading a book, check to see if there are other ways to tell how different translators treated the book.

9. Determine who the narrator is. Try to identify the poet in the poem. Is it told from a first-person, second-person, or third-person perspective? What is the narration style used by the narrator? The speaker's identity influences the story's interpretation based on their personal experience.

10. Line by line, the poem is described. Go back to the poem once more, and repeat it. Paraphrasedoutput: paraphrasedoutput: start with the first line and end with the second line. In other words, interpret the meaning by writing down your summary as you go. Once you've completed the whole poem, read your words to grasp the meaning of it.

In Conclusion when considering how to analyze a poem, it's important to come up with a specific conclusion. First and foremost, repeat the thesis in different ways. Describe the most important findings to support the hypothesis. From this, you can formulate your own opinions and take a step back and consider what it all means by focusing on one single point. Lastly, try to provide the reader with something

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memorable to take away with them (a thought-provoking sentence or question about the poem).

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